

Effect of rice varieties on the parasitism of AfRGM by *Platygaster diplosisae* and *Aprostocetus procerae* and the percentage of tillers with galls. Means (\pm S.E.) within a row for each parasitoid followed by the same letter are not significantly different at $P>0.05$; least significant difference.

high level of parasitism in the four varieties suggests that host plants offer no antagonistic effects to AfRGM parasitoids. The plant resistance factors in NHTA8 and Eguazankpa did not influence parasitoid activity or level of parasitism under no-choice conditions, indicating that the interaction between host-plant resistance and AfRGM parasitoids would thus be synergistic or additive and could result in successful integration of these two important pest management options. This is particularly important in the integrated pest management of AfRGM for which desirable levels of resistance have not yet been achieved.

Results, however, might differ under free-choice conditions. Tritrophic interactions should be explored by plant breeders and insect ecologists who aim to produce resistant varieties which, when infested, still produce volatiles in sufficient amounts to attract parasitoids or preda-

tors. With recent advances in hybridization and molecular markers at WARDA, efforts are under way to increase rice resistance and understanding of such tritrophic interactions in cereal-based ecosystems.

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Ecological characterization of biotic constraints to rice in Cambodia

G.C. Jahn, EPPD, IRRI; Pheng Sophea, School of Land and Food, University of Queensland, St. Lucia, Australia; Khiev Bunnarith and Pol Chanty, Cambodia-IRRI-Australia Project (CIAP), P.O. Box 1, Phnom Penh, Cambodia
E-mail: irri-cambodia@cgiar.org

From 1994 to 1998, a total of 73 rainfed lowland rice fields (RLR) (>0.3 ha each) in Cambodia were studied to determine which pests affect yields and how cropping practices affect pest levels. From 1997 to 2000, this information was used to generate testable hypotheses for crop protection research and to help prioritize the integrated pest management (IPM) research program of CIAP. The data collection methods of Savary et al (1996) were adapted to Cambodian conditions. “Pests” included insects, weeds, and diseases. Farmer interviews (Jahn et al 1997b), pest collections, and practical considerations (e.g., ease of recognizing the pest or its damage) were used to determine which pests to include

in the study. Pesticides were not used in any of the fields in this study.

Data were gathered at four crop development stages: tillering, booting, milk, and maturity. The yield of each field was estimated by averaging the weights of three randomly selected $2 \times 5\text{-m}^2$ harvested areas, converted to t ha^{-1} and adjusted to 14% moisture. Pest incidence was recorded from 10 hills chosen haphazardly from each field. Weed infestation was measured as the percentage weed cover in three 1-m^2 areas that included sampling hill number 3, 6, and 9. The analysis proceeded in five steps: (1) determination of average injury levels of each pest for each crop stage, (2) categorization of variables (i.e.,

pest, cropping practices, and yield) into classes, (3) testing for independence of paired variables (i.e., pest levels, cropping practices, and yields) in contingency tables, (4) clustering of cropping practices, yields, and pest profiles, and (5) development of contingency tables and correspondence analysis. Data were analyzed with Excel® and STAT-ITCF®.

Correspondence analysis between combined variables (i.e., cropping practices and pest profiles) and yields resulted in the formation of four domains (see figure). Low levels of gall midge damage (i.e., 0–0.2% tiller damage) were recorded in the highest yielding fields (domain D, table). The lowest yielding fields had high

Graphical display of correspondence analysis of the biotic constraint data matrix. The cropping practice (CP), yield (Y), and pest (PE) clusters can be grouped into four domains described in the table.

Characteristics of the domains derived from Figure 1.

Domain	Clusters	Cropping practices and yields	Pest constraints
A	Y1, CP1 PE4	Late-duration rice varieties and some medium varieties Low application of mineral fertilizer Very diverse water management Very low yield	Weeds, gall midge, cut worm, and brown spot
B	Y2, CP4 PE3	Early rice varieties Low application of mineral fertilizer Water depths very diverse Low yield	Brown spot, gall midge, sucking insects
C	Y3, CP3 PE1	Medium rice varieties High application of minerals Too much water Medium yield	Weeds, whorl maggot, hispa, sucking insects, and gall midge
D	Y4, CP2	Medium cultivars and some early varieties High application of mineral fertilizer and manure Little standing water High yield	Narrow brown spot

levels of gall midge (1–59% tiller damage), cutworm (15–51% leaf damage), brown spot (32–94% leaf damage), and weeds (10–30% weed cover) (domain A, table).

Study results led the CIAP IPM Program to assess the importance of gall midge in different parts of Cambodia and to conduct field trials to evaluate varietal resistance to gall midge (Jahn et al 1997a, Jahn and Khiev 1998). From 1998 to 2000, CIAP conducted experiments to test hypotheses generated by the characterization study, including whether the levels of pest damage recorded in the characterization study could actually reduce yields (see Khiev, “Effects of simulated pest damage on rice yields,” p 27–28); how well early and medium-duration varieties compete against weeds; and investigations on the interactions of fertilizer, variety, pests, and yield.

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